

Using ABMs for Prediction: Two thought experiments and a workshop

Gary Polhill, Matt Hare, David Anzola, Tom Bauermann, Thomas French, Hanna Post, Doug Salt

The James
Hutton
Institute

Outline

- Motivation:
 - The Unpredictability of Complex Systems
- Thought experiment 1
 - Finding Transition Functions in Cellular Automata
- Thought experiment 2
 - Asynchronous Turing Machine Networks
- Workshop
 - Is Wickedness the Real Problem?

A pragmatic view of prediction

- Edmonds (2017)
 - *Reliably generate*
 - i.e. not a matter of luck whether you turn out to be right
 - something *unknown*
 - Need not be the future
 - Could be a class rather than the value of a variable
 - to a *useful degree of accuracy*
 - Usefulness is a social construction defined by context
 - 1 significant figure could be enough (for numeric values)
 - using the *model*
 - i.e. based on clear interpretation of model behaviour

Complex Systems

- Ill-defined (Mitchell 2009)
- Thurner et al. (2017)
 - Interactions of elements with heterogeneous attributes mediated through networks
 - Lots of ‘maybes’
 - Different kinds of interaction at the same time
 - Chaotic / nonlinear dynamics
 - Exogenously driven
 - Out-of-equilibrium
 - Non-ergodic
 - Some possible states of the system are unreachable from some other states

Complexity Denialism

Complexity averages out or disappears at the 'right scale'

"You are here"

By NASA/JPL/SSI/CICLOPS - <http://www.jpl.nasa.gov/spaceimages/details.php?id=PIA17171>
<http://photojournal.jpl.nasa.gov/catalog/PIA17171>

Public Domain: <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=27393467>

Monomorphic Complexity

- One class of entity operating at a single spatio-temporal scale
- With ‘simple behavioural rules’
- Emphasis on emergence...
- ... and “no central control”

The James
Hutton
Institute

Prediction in Complex Systems

- Often glibly stated to be impossible
 - Not unreasonably!
 - e.g. three body problem
- Leads to papers telling you all the other useful things you can do with models
 - e.g. Epstein (2008) “Why Model?” JASSS 11/4/12
- But a key requirement in many contexts
 - If we don't do it someone else will

Eight Kinds of Predictability

- Invariable Predictability
 - Same value regardless of transition function
- Omissive Predictability
 - Some values never appear regardless of t.f.
- Asymmetric Unpredictability
 - Any value is possible, but not equally possible
- Symmetric Unpredictability
 - All values are equally possible

Cell

System

Eight Kinds of Predictability

- ←

Invariable Predictability

 - Same value regardless of transition function

Best case; least likely

- Omissive Predictability**

 - Some values never appear regardless of t.f.
- Asymmetric Unpredictability**

 - Any value is possible, but not equally possible

- Symmetric Unpredictability**

 - All values are equally possible

Worst case: ruled out at system level by non-Ergodicity?

Eight Kinds of Predictability

The James
Hutton
Institute

Individual
Invariable

2-state

Individual
Omissive

System
Invariable

Must be
 ≥ 1 not
invariable
individual

System
Omissive

Must be ≥ 1
invariable
or omissive
individual

System
Symmetric

Individual
Symmetric

≥ 1 asymm. indiv.

Epsilon

Individual
Asymmetric

System
Asymmetric

Finding CA Transition Functions

- Cellular Automata are a simple class of spatially-explicit model with surprisingly complex dynamics
 - Regular grid of cells
 - Each cell can have one of a finite number of states
 - State at time $t + 1$ is a **function** of state at time t and states of neighbours at time t
 - **Function** is the ‘**transition function**’ of the CA
 - Synchronous scheduling
- Simplest case of 1D CA
 - Cells form a line
 - Each cell has state 1 or 0
 - State at time $t + 1$ is a function of own state and that of left and right neighbours

1D CA unpredictability

- So-called ‘Class IV’ CAs argued to be unpredictable *except through simulation*
 - Wolfram (1983)
- Rule ‘110’ is TM equivalent
 - Cook (2004)

All 8 possible states at t affecting the outcome of the **centre** cell at $t + 1$

In which of the states does the **centre** cell have state 1 at time $t + 1$?

1D CA Predictability

- Given ≥ 2 snapshots from a CA:
 - Find transition function(s) that generate the latest snapshot given earlier one(s)
 - Simulate them to predict a future state
- Big search!
 - k^{k^n}
 - k = state set size
 - n = number of neighbours
 - e.g. simple 1D CA = $2^{2^3} = 256$
 - one more state $3^3 \sim 20K$
 - one more neighbour $2^{2^5} \sim 4.3G!$
 - But infeasible (in general) not undecidable

Later state

(Somewhat odd)

Example

Asynchronous TM Networks

- Multiple TMs all using the same tape
 - Analogous to parallelism
 - Synchronized: does not change computability
 - Predictable or computable order of execution of each TM
 - Asynchronous: provably super-Turing
 - Non-computable order of execution of each TM
 - Copeland & Sylvan (1999)
- In the 1D CA context
 - Update a random cell
- Fitting to snapshots: much bigger search space! (But still finite)
 - $(c!)^t \times k^{k^n}$
 - c = number of cells in each snapshot
 - $c!$ ways of ordering them
 - t = number of time steps between first and last snapshot

Synchronized

Rule 110

Not Synchronized

Workshop on Prediction (Stockholm)

- SWOT analysis of ABM for prediction
 - Strengths: predicting unlikely events, possible worlds
 - Weaknesses: unmanaged expectations, requirement for ‘point’ prediction, lack of methods, lack of data
 - Opportunities: whole-system view, integration and disaffection with established practice
 - Threats: resurgence of AI/ML with ‘big’ (-ish) data, need to show order-of-magnitude improvement over established methods, any perceptions of previous ABM work where believed not to have delivered what was promised

Workshop on Prediction (Stockholm)

- Discussion on prediction challenge in five case studies
 - Ecological succession; Swedish general election; amplitude of predator-prey cycles; weather; positions of planets
 - What do we need to know?
 - Too much! Data and/or knowledge may be contested, or not accessible
 - Who voted what last time?
 - What's the population of species X in area Y over the last 100 years?
 - How would we check our predictions were right?
 - Hindcasting
 - But what if data are contested?
 - What if fitting the past isn't convincing about the future?
 - What gives us confidence in our predictions?
 - Usual numerical metrics (where possible)
 - What's 'in' the model (assumptions)
 - Other people have made similar predictions...

Wicked Systems

- Rittel & Porter (1973): “Wicked Problems”
 - No definitive formulation
 - No definitive solution
 - It matters if you’re wrong
- Andersson et al. (2014; 2018): “Wicked Systems”
 - Complicated and complex
 - Complicated: composed of many entities of many types at multiple scales
 - Complex: one entity type, many many entities, emergence
 - Wicked: co-adaptation of components operating at multiple levels, lock-ins and cascades
- Interpretation here:
 - More than one way to model it
 - cf. Perl: [TMTOWTDI](#)
 - So the search space increases even further...
 - ... or maybe is unbounded:
 - “There’s always another way to model it”

Hierarchy of Prediction Search Space (CA)

m : number of options
 c : number of cells
 t : number of time steps
 k : number of states
 n : number of neighbours

Hierarchy of Prediction Search Space (CA)

m : number of options
 c : number of cells
 t : number of time steps
 k : number of states
 n : number of neighbours

Gotts et al. [in press](#)
Ecological Complexity

Summary

- Complexity makes prediction difficult
 - Intractable rather than impossible
 - Super-exponential, but finite, space to search
- Wickedness is a greater challenge
 - If the conjecture that ‘there’s always another way to model it’ is true, then the search space is unbounded

Work in this paper has been supported by:

- The Scottish Government Environment, Agriculture and Food Strategic Research Portfolio 2016-2021
 - Theme 2: Productive and Sustainable Land Management and Rural Economies
- The Macaulay Development Trust
 - Project no. E000956
- European Commission Horizon 2020 project SMARTEES
 - Grant agreement no. 763912
- Research Council of Norway
 - Project no. 244608

We are grateful to Toni Perelló Moragues who participated in the workshop, but preferred not to be listed as a co-author.

Scottish Government
Riaghaltas na h-Alba
gov.scot